

Interview Guide – IWT Transport

Interview Guide for Expert Interviews on Attribute Validation for a Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE)

Interviewee Name:

Company:

Date:

Interviewer:

Dear XXX,

Thank you for taking the time to participate in this interview. The interview is conducted as part of my Master's thesis at the University of Applied Sciences BFI Vienna and is embedded in the broader research framework of Denise Beil's PhD project at the University of Antwerp.

Brief Description of the Master's Thesis:

The core focus of my thesis is the empirical preparation of a Stated Preference Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) to analyze decision-making behavior in European freight transport along the TEN-T Rhine-Danube Corridor. The aim of these expert interviews is to define realistic and practice-relevant value ranges for key transport attributes (costs, transit time, reliability, frequency) and to understand how shippers and logistics service providers (LSPs) evaluate trade-offs between these criteria.

In this interview, we aim to:

- Empirically narrow down the relevant value ranges (min–max spans) for key attributes (costs, transit time, reliability, frequency) and transport modes (road, rail, inland waterway) along selected origin-destination (OD) routes of the TEN-T Rhine-Danube Corridor;
- Validate the composition, interpretation, and perceived importance of these attributes;

- Understand the cognitive decision-making logic of shippers and LSPs regarding trade-offs between attributes;
- Identify critical interactions and threshold values required for modeling realistic DCE choice sets based on ex-ante validated data.

Duration and Procedure:

The interview follows a semi-structured format and will take approximately 60 minutes. It includes tables for quantitative assessment and supplementary questions on practical relevance and interpretation. If desired, you may review the tables in advance.

All information will be treated confidentially and used exclusively in anonymized form for academic purposes.

Thank you in advance for your time - I am looking forward to your insights and your valuable practical perspective!

Henrike Bauer & Denise Beil

1. Company Characteristics (Demographic Context)

Objective: To control for structural influencing factors in later modeling (heterogeneity)

- Company type (shipper, trade, LSP, carrier, other):

- Company size (number of employees, revenue class, locations):

- Position of interviewee (strategic/operational, dispatch, management):
- Main customers (industry, trade, 3PL, etc.): _____
- Frequency of cross-border transports in the TEN-T Rhine-Danube corridor:

2. Context Screening: Use of OD Routes and Transport Modes

Objective: To ensure full coverage of the five predefined DCE routes – no omission per interview.

Which of the following OD routes are you familiar with or have actively used in the past? Which transport modes do you primarily use per route on a regular basis?

Main transport mode used (Road / Rail / Inland Waterway):

Route	Connection	Countries	Actively used? (Yes/No)
R1	Strasbourg – Wels/Linz (via Stuttgart/München)	FR, DE, AT	
R4	Wien/Bratislava – Budapest – Timisoara	AT, SK HU, RO	
R5	Wien/Bratislava – Constanța	AT, SK, HU, RO	

3. Data Basis for DCE Modelling: Empirical Attribute Assessment Along Defined Relations and Transport Modes

In this interview, all questions related to transport cost, transit time, reliability, and frequency refer to the complete door-to-door transport process between two company locations along the defined routes.

- For rail and inland waterway transports, we consider intermodal freight transport with containerized loading units, including pre- and post-haulage by truck.
- For road transport, we assume classic road freight transport as a direct, uninterrupted delivery – this is not intermodal but likewise door-to-door. Our aim is to make all input as comparable as possible across the full transport process – regardless of the transport mode.

• **Transport cost:** Please relate your estimates – if possible – to the entire door-to-door transport. Approximate values and value ranges in €/tonne-kilometre are also helpful to us.

• **Transit time:** This refers to the typical duration from loading at the sender to unloading at the receiver – that is, the complete door-to-door time.

• **Reliability:** This refers to the share of transports that arrive within the agreed time window. – 90% IWT / Railway 80/85% - daily punctuality

• **Frequency:** This represents flexibility and refers to the realistically feasible number of transports per week on a given route – regardless of how many actually take place at present. Weekly / depends on market / demand situation / daily

What we ask of you in advance:

Please review the tables for the respective routes and attributes and complete them – based on your experience – with typical, minimum, and maximum values. This helps us to structure the discussion of deviations from literature values and special remarks during the interview

- **Before the interview** review the reference tables for each route and attribute.
- Enter your typical, minimum, and maximum values based on your experience.
- If your experience differs from the literature-based ranges, please specify your values and explain why.

Why Extreme Values Are Included:

Extreme values (e.g., for cost, time, or reliability) represent rare but real situations—such as severe low water, major infrastructure failures, or extraordinary demand spikes—that can temporarily push figures beyond normal market conditions. These help us understand the full range of operational realities and are important for robust modeling.

Examples of Extreme Situations

- **Transport Costs (0.06–0.075 €/tkm):**
These values were observed during the 2022 low-water crisis on the Rhine and Danube. Exceptionally low river levels drastically reduced vessel capacity, while fuel prices surged due to geopolitical tensions. This combination led to sharp, temporary spikes in freight rates.
- **Transit Time (up to 7 days):**
Severe disruptions such as prolonged lock closures, ice, flooding, or extended low water can delay shipments for days.
- **Reliability (down to 40%):**
In years with persistent hydrological constraints or major infrastructure failures, the share of on-time arrivals can drop significantly.

R1 – Strasbourg – Wels/Linz (via Stuttgart/München)

Attribute	Literature Range	Average Literature	Typical (Practice)	Minimum (Practice)	Maximum (Practice)	Extreme Value
Transport Costs (€/tkm)	0.020 – 0.037	0.03				0.06–0.075
Transit Time (Days)	6 – 14	8-10				20
Reliability (%)	65 – 80	70				50-60
Frequency (Departures/Wk)	1 – 2	1.5				

Additional comments or contextual explanations (e.g., seasonal variation, infrastructure constraints, regulatory impact):

R4 – Wien/Bratislava – Budapest – Timisoara

Attribute	Literature Range	Average Literature	Typical (Practice)	Minimum (Practice)	Maximum (Practice)	Extreme Value
Transport Costs (€/tkm)	0.020 – 0.037	0.03				0.06– 0.075
Transit Time (Days)	6 – 14	8-10				20
Reliability (%)	65 – 80	70				50-60
Frequency (Departures/Wk)	1 – 2	1.5				

Additional comments or contextual explanations (e.g., seasonal variation, infrastructure constraints, regulatory impact):

R5 – Wien/Bratislava – Constanța

Attribute	Literature Range	Average Literature	Typical (Practice)	Minimum (Practice)	Maximum (Practice)	Extreme Value
Transport Costs (€/tkm)	0.020 – 0.037	0.03				0.06– 0.075
Transit Time (Days)	6 – 14	8-10				20
Reliability (%)	65 – 80	70				50-60
Frequency (Departures/Wk)	1 – 2	1.5				

Additional comments or contextual explanations (e.g., seasonal variation, infrastructure constraints, regulatory impact):

A1. Key Data on Transport Costs

Optional comment – Are there any specific framework conditions that influence your estimate?

(e.g., seasonal or regional variations, political measures, operational constraints)

What determines the level of transport costs on this relation?

Tolls Energy Labour Handling Equipment Other: running cost / cost of the asset _____

How sensitive are shippers to cost differences?

- Very sensitive (even small differences trigger changes)
- Moderately sensitive (only substantial differences have an effect)
- Hardly sensitive (other factors dominate)
- Cannot be answered in general – please explain:

Are deviations of $\pm 25\%$ from typical transport costs still realistic in your experience? 0-75% percent depending on waterlevel

Yes No Depends on the relation or transport mode – please comment:

How realistic do you find the given literature-based value ranges?

- Align with practice Narrower than real-life experience
- Broader than real-life experience Not applicable to our situation

Explanation:

A2. Key Data on Transit Time

Optional comment – Are there any specific framework conditions that influence your estimate?

What are the main factors influencing transit time?

- Border crossings only in case of crossing Serbia (planned since daily)
- Handling Timetables Infrastructure
- Capacity Weather Other: _____

Do shippers require specific delivery time windows (e.g. fixed delivery slots or advance notice)?

How tolerant are your clients towards deviations from the expected transit time? (e.g. ± 1 day, ± 6 hours)

Are $\pm 25\%$ deviations from typical transit times still realistic in your experience?

Yes No Depends on the relation or mode – please comment:

How realistic do you find the given literature-based value ranges?

Align with practice Narrower than real-life experience

Broader than real-life experience Not applicable to our situation

Explanation:

A3. Key Data on Reliability

Optional comment – Are there any specific framework conditions that influence your estimate?

How do you assess the average reliability per mode along the OD relations you use?

Are there significant differences between routes or countries?

Road: _____

Rail: boarder crossings _____

Inland Waterway: Serbia IWT differs a lot

Which factors influence reliability along this route?

Weather Boarder crossings Staff knowledge of waterway is essential availability

IT systems Coordination Other: _____

How do you define punctuality in your daily practice?

Same-day arrival acceptable ± 2 hours tolerance

- Pre-agreed ETA delivery window Any deviation is acceptable if consistent
 Other: _____

What level of reliability is still acceptable to you? When does it become critical or lead to modal exclusion?

- Road: _____
 Rail: _____
 Inland Waterway: _____

Are $\pm 25\%$ deviations from typical reliability rates still plausible in your experience?

- Yes No Depends on the route – please comment:
Comment: _____

How realistic do you find the given literature-based value ranges?

- Align with practice Narrower than real-life experience
 Broader than real-life experience Not applicable to our situation

Explanation:

A4. Key Data on Frequency

Optional comment – Are there any specific framework conditions that influence your estimate?

How many departures per week are typical or realistically possible for this mode on this route?

Answer: _Daily if demand is there _____

How stable is this frequency over the year?

(e.g., seasonal variation, capacity constraints, weather-related)

Answer: ___yes seasonal and capacity constraints and weather

Which factors influence the regularity of departures?

- Seasonal variation Volume of demand Timetable reliability
 Staff availability Other: _____

From what minimum frequency onward would you consider a mode suitable for regular use?

Are $\pm 25\%$ deviations from typical frequency levels still plausible in your experience?

Yes No Depends on the relation – please comment:

Comment: _____

How realistic do you find the given literature-based value ranges?

Align with practice Narrower than real-life experience

Broader than real-life experience Not applicable to our situation

Explanation:

4. Trade-Offs and Decision Logics

- **Which attribute most strongly influences your modal choice – and why?**

Answer: _ _____

- **How do you weigh costs vs. transit time? Are there thresholds at which modal shifts become likely?**

Answer: _ _____

- **To what extent is reliability considered in your operational decisions?**

Answer: _____

- **Which hidden/additional costs affect your decisions (e.g. storage due to delay)?**

Answer: _____

- **What role do political or regulatory factors play (e.g. tolls, CO₂ pricing)?**

Answer: __ _____

- **What change in an attribute (e.g. -20% cost or +10% reliability) would trigger a realistic shift?**

Answer: _____

- **Are there absolute exclusion criteria (e.g. <60% reliability)?**

Answer: _____

- **How do you prioritise economic vs. temporal and operational attributes?**

Answer: _____

5. Attribute Validation and Additional Aspects

- Do you feel that any relevant attribute is missing?

Answer: _____

- Would you be willing to participate in a pretest of the choice sets with hypothetical scenarios?

Answer: _____

- Are there any important aspects that are underrepresented in the modal shift debate?

Answer: _____

6. Influence of Cargo Type on Transport Mode Choice

Question:

Does the type of cargo you transport influence your choice of transport mode?

If yes: For which of the following cargo types is the choice of transport mode particularly relevant in your decision-making?

(Multiple answers possible)

- High-value goods
- Time-sensitive or perishable goods
- Bulk cargo / high-volume commodities
- No significant difference between cargo types
- Other – please comment: high and heavy _____

Optional comment:

Reference Values and Sources

All ranges and extreme values in the tables are based on recognized scientific studies, EU reports, and official annual reports relevant to the TEN-T Rhine-Danube Corridor.